

ISSUES OF EVOLUTIONARY DEVELOPMENT IN THE SYSTEM OF SIMPLE SENTENCES OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE (20TH CENTURY)

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Resume: In the article, the issues of development in the field of the syntax of the Uzbek literary language were considered, the changes in the syntactic structures of the Uzbek language under the influence of linguistic and non-linguistic factors were studied on the basis of materials of the 20th century and they were compared to the materials of the old Uzbek language.

Key words: syntax, development, linguistic and extralinguistic factors, syntactic devices, old Uzbek language, modern Uzbek language, syntactic redistribution, functional sentence types.

The Uzbek language has been experiencing evolutionary development trends based on the needs of the people's communicative process for centuries. In particular, the 20th century was one of the periods that left a significant mark on the development of the Uzbek language. It can be seen as an objective fact that the historical changes that occurred in the life of the people during this period, the rapid progress in the political, economic and cultural spheres that took place in the development of the society, and the innovations in the field of press, mass information, school and education played an important role in the evolutionary development of the Uzbek language.

By this time, the changes that occurred in the system of simple sentences of the Uzbek literary language, firstly, with the evolution and improvement of the sentence forms in the old Uzbek literary language, secondly, with the widespread use of compact, effective syntactic constructions typical of the current Uzbek literary language, and thirdly, the blessing of other languages as a result of its influence, some syntactic constructions appeared and strengthened. The first and second of them can be evaluated as the results of the linguistic development of the Uzbek language based on its own internal resources, and the third as an external influence, an extralinguistic factor. As a result of these factors, the following changes occurred in the development of the system of simple sentences of the Uzbek language in the 20th century:

1. In the old Uzbek language, the case of dropping or keeping the possessive was widely used, and there were certain reasons for its dropping. According to researchers, the first sentence of a work or text, a new paragraph, composed of the author's sentence, is always possessive, and the possessive may be omitted in subsequent sentences. (1, 1). By the grace of God Almighty and by the intercession of His Holiness the Lord of the Universe and by the efforts of the holy people, on Tuesday, the fifth of the month of Ramadan, in the year eight hundred and ninety-nine, I became a twelve-year-old king in Ferghana region (from "Boburnoma"). In the works published in the 20s of the XX century, the hiding of the owner and the preserved cases were used. Anyway, it is more common in the old Uzbek language compared to the modern Uzbek language.

2. In the old Uzbek language, the words kamina, fakir, qul, which denote the possessive function, were used as a personal pronoun. This statement expressed humility. Fakir also told a story and a ghazal (Ogahi). I was a thirteen-fourteen-year-old boy in that area. (Odil Yakupov, "Diyonat"). Nowadays, these words are not used in the possessive function, and this is due to an extralinguistic reason. It has become a tradition to use the pronoun "we" instead of "I" in order to express humility.

3. In modern Uzbek language, it is a literary norm to use the verb participle in the singular form when it is a singular collective noun denoting possessive persons. The regiment returned to the front line at the end of May. (A. Qahhor). In the old Uzbek language, in such cases, the participle is often used in the plural form.

This is evident in the written sources of the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century: Andagm people donated ten thousand soums to build a madrasa called a gymnasium for the education of young girls ("Turkistan region" newspaper). In such sentences, the use of the participle in the plural continued in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century: The courtiers returned to their rooms freed from their day's work ("Otkan kunlar"). In the modern Uzbek literary language, it is decided as a literary standard that if the participle is singular and the participle is singular, and the participle is plural if it is represented by a collective noun: The peoples want peace - the peoples want peace.

4. In the old Uzbek language, the definite article all, bari, all, which means to generalize, come in the singular form when the participle is plural: Everyone turned their faces to prayer ("The days gone by"). In the modern Uzbek language, the possessive participles expressed by the singular pronouns "bari", "all", "all" come in the singular number. Only poetic works are excluded from this.

5. In modern Uzbek, there are two situations in the compatibility of the participle with the third person possessive:

a) when referring to inanimate objects in the plural, the participle is always used in the singular (The flowers have opened. The fields are being plowed):

b) the participle can be used both in the singular and in the plural when referring to living objects with a plural number (The children are going to school. The children are going to school). In the old Uzbek language, when referring to inanimate objects, the participle was also used in the plural (I later found out that from the Turkic word, ta and dal are interchangeable with each other with the help of local economy). Such a situation can be seen in the publications published in the 20s of the 20th century. Red carpets and royal blankets filled the house. (1924 edition of "Bygone Days"). These indicate that the tradition of the old Uzbek literary language continued at the beginning of the 20th century, and this tradition became even more popular under the influence of the Russian language in later times, which is confirmed in the press materials: construction organizations perform construction and assembly work worth 120 thousand som (Toshken Akshomi newspaper)). Prof. A.G. Ghulamov assessed: "This increase in adaptation is one of the facts that shows the progressive role and influence of the Russian language in the development of the Uzbek language" (2,92).

6. In the Uzbek language, the suffix -s ensures the plural compatibility of the participle with ega. In verb participles, the suffix -(i)sh can also reveal such a match. In fact -(i)sh suffix is used to form the singular aspect of the verb. In the materials of the 20s of the 20th century, this form does not indicate the plural. By the 1930s, the occurrence of this form in the plural function becomes a little more active: Mirsoat and Anavi are moved by Mulla Obid's determination.

7. Over time, there have been significant changes in the development of plant forms. Structural and functional changes have occurred especially in the use of nouns. It is known that in Uzbek, the noun participle often comes in the form of a preposition. But since the 30s and 40s of the 20th century, the nouns used in conjunctions of place, exit, and departure began to be used as participles. Such nouns were actually used in a secondary role, according to the usual rule. As a

result of the falling or hiding of the cut, such secondary pieces also take on the function of the cut. For example, for the anniversary of our Victory-capital. Scientific achievements - to the economy. Vegetables for the table of our fellow villagers (Tashkent evening). The appearance of such constructions in the syntactic structure of the Uzbek language was a direct result of the translation of such sentences in the Russian language.

Also, in the modern Uzbek language, the word in the accusative case does not function as participle. In the old Uzbek language, they were used as participles together with conjunctions. This can be seen in the following examples: This stick is the tour of Moses ("Tafsir" page 28). Whose is this reed? Aydi: This boy's turur (Rabguzi, p. 31). This matla is aningdurkim (Navoiyy).

A. Matgoziev notes that the forms of - and - are used in the Uzbek language of the 19th century as participles (pages 3, 31-32). This letter is from someone else. Is it a continent or something else (Badoe-ul waqae (242.59 b). Later, the accusative affix -niki was formed and the participle form was formed.

8. In the construction of the syntax of the old Uzbek language, the role of the conjunction was extremely large. He actively participated in the participle function with the participle. With the passage of time, the connections have changed, and as a result of historical development, they have come to the form of turur durur erur dur dir.

In the current Uzbek language - dir is not used in I, II persons. Its function is occupied by the verb forms - man, - san, - you, - miz, the form - dir is used only in the third person. This is used only in the third person. This is explained by the fact that the third person does not have a formal indicator. For example: I am a student. You are a student. He is a student.

9. In the syntactic construction of the Uzbek language, as a result of the syntactic re-division, the syntactic constructions gained compactness, smoothness and smoothness, and caused the functional change of the parts of the sentence. Prof. A. Ghulomov, he needs to go - He needs to go. I have to say- I have to say.

We have to do - We have to do, that the constructions of the type have changed as a result of the development of the language, that in these constructions, his, my, our particles are demonstrative determiners, the particles of go, say, do have, the particles of must, must, should have become participles, due to the development of the language, this

points out that the clauses are combined to form a participle, that the word in the nominative case is used in the main case and is transferred to the possessive function, and this is a syntactic re-division (2.73). As a result of the evolutionary development of the language, the attributive compound has become a predicative compound. In the 20s and 30s of the last century, these two forms were used twice, from the middle of the 30s, the use of the predicative compound form became active and won over the attributive form. Today, the use of the predicative conjunction is established as a literary norm.

In the development of the Uzbek language in the 20th century, under the influence of a number of linguistic and non-linguistic factors, many changes took place in the system of active and inactive constructions, and in the functional types of sentences. In particular, new structural changes have occurred in the construction of indicative, interrogative, and command sentences, which can be evaluated in terms of the influence of non-linguistic factors on language development. These are detailed in some sources. (4.183-187). So, the evolutionary pace of language development has been constantly developing on the basis of these two factors, which leaves its significant traces in the field of grammar as well as in other fields.

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